

Discovery of one 23-Digit Palindromic Prime in the Decimal Expansion of π

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1 Introduction

On January 16, 2026, a computational search was conducted to identify palindromic prime numbers of length 23 within the $25.9 \times 10^{12} - 26 \times 10^{12}$ - decimal digits of the mathematical constant π (approximately 3.141592653589793238462643383...). Using a modified C program with streaming capabilities to handle a 100 GB file containing the decimal expansion of π , one palindromic prime were discovered. A palindromic prime is a number that is both a palindrome (reads the same forwards and backwards) and a prime number. This document presents the positions of this palindrome in the decimal expansion of π . The detailed results, including certificate of primality and a confirmation of the absolute position using y-cruncher BBP Pi Digit Extractor, are available on ZENODO.

2 Results

The following list enumerates the palindromic prime of length 23 found in the decimal expansion of π , along with its starting and ending positions (1-based indexing, relative to the first decimal digit after the decimal point in π):

1. **Palindrome: 36683591459995419538663**
Positions: 25921378508088 - 25921378508110

3 Methodology

The search was performed using a new (than the previous used program) custom C program employing the GMP library for arbitrary-precision arithmetic and multi-threading for efficiency. The program processed a 100 GB file containing 1×10^{11} decimal digits of π , using a streaming approach to minimize memory usage. The search targeted palindromes of length 23 within the interval $[25.9 \times 10^{12} - 26 \times 10^{12}]$, the search duration was approximately 15 minutes. The certificate of primality for the discovered palindrome is archived on ZENODO for public access.